

INNOVATIVE GLASS-CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES: PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION

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1 Introduction

A new generation of glass-ceramic matrices for structural composites was developed for continuous thermal exposure applications [1]. These new matrices are obtained after a specific heat treatment of an inorganic thermosetting polymer derived from a geopolymeric system [2-3]. One advantage of these new composites is that they can be manufactured using the conventional organic matrix composites processes. Indeed, the inorganic resin hardening occurs at a temperature lower than 100°C. Besides, owing to their inorganic nature, these matrices allow obtaining composites that offer a high temperature resistance and structural properties comparable to conventional ceramic matrix composites. Thereby, these materials are good candidates to bridge the gap between organic matrix composites and ceramic matrix composites.

This research work is part of a collaborative project called 'COMPTINN' (INNOvative COMPOSITE materials for intermediate Temperature applications). It aims at enabling the manufacturing of competitive structural composites able to withstand continuous thermal exposure such as in aircraft parts located close to the engines. The research is led in partnership with Pyromeral Systems and Herakles companies.

A prepreg process is currently used to manufacture these glass-ceramic matrix composites because of the quite high resin viscosity. However, composites would be more competitive for aircraft industry if they were produced by an easy and cost effective processing technology. Well-known liquid moulding techniques, such as liquid resin infusion (LRI) or

resin transfer moulding (RTM), seem to be a convenient solution. The rheological behaviour of the considered inorganic polymer was previously investigated [4]. The best conditions were identified to obtain the lowest viscosity of the resin in order to help the production of structural composite parts by liquid moulding. Besides, as the resin is an aqueous suspension, one way to decrease its viscosity is to increase the water content. But, the water dilution of the resin impact on the composite properties has to be known. A previous work, to study the impact of the resin water content on composites tensile properties made by prepreg process, shows that: when water is added in a too small quantity, composites exhibit an elastic and quite brittle behaviour. When water is added in a sufficient quantity, the behaviour changes: these composites exhibit an enhanced damage tolerance. Resin diluted with this amount of water will be referred in this paper as "diluted resin" to keep the amount of water confidential.

The research work presented in this paper investigates how changes in the manufacturing process impact mechanical properties of the composites. A microstructural characterization links the mechanical behaviour to the processing route.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The composite materials were manufactured with various processing techniques and reinforcements. This paper focuses on prepreg and RTM ($\Delta P=3\text{bars}$) processes. Two kind of reinforcements were considered: a layup of several two-dimensional

woven fabric plies and a three-dimensional preform. Two carbon fiber grades were used, referred to as 'grade 1' and 'grade 2' fibers. Two-dimensional fabrics are made with grade 1 fibers, and three-dimensional preform with grade 2 fibers. The matrix comes from the inorganic resin, which was used as manufactured or after water addition. This paper is dealing with six materials. Table 1 sums up composite material details. All the materials are postcured at high temperature. Several studies are reported in the literature about composite manufactured with a geopolymeric matrix [5, 6]. But the glass-ceramic matrix of the materials studied in this paper has completely different properties.

Three coupons were tested for both materials processed by prepreg. Four or five coupons are cut throughout the plates manufactured by RTM. The impact of the position of the coupon in the plate made by RTM process on the properties is studied too. In the presented results, the impact of the position was slight. In any case, differences between each specimen are included in standard deviation data. Results obtained for the 6 composite materials will be presented in this paper.

Table 2 gives the mean thickness, fiber volume fraction and open porosity of each material. Open porosity was measured by imbibition and Archimedes methods. Thanks to these methods, open porosity is estimated with three weight values. One with a dry sample in air, the second and third weight values are obtained with a water imbibited sample in air and in water. Open porosity values of the 'prepreg_2D', 'RTM_2D' and 'RTM_3D' materials, made from an undiluted resin, are respectively of 18.4%, 25.1% and 27.1%. For Prepreg_2D composites, open porosity is increasing with the water dilution of the matrix precursor to 20.3%. For the RTM_2D composites, the amount of open porosities is constant. For the RTM_3D composites, the amount of open porosities is increasing to 28.1%. For ceramic matrix composites, usual fiber volume fractions range from 35% to 45%. Values obtained in the present study are in this range. The fiber volume fraction is one of the most important factor that controls the mechanical behaviour of composites. The higher the fiber volume fraction, the higher the composite strength and stiffness. In this study, values are quite close. Besides, specimen thickness plays a role in tension

tests because the load is transferred by friction at the grips. Thinner samples could provide better results.

2.2 Methods

Unloading-reloading tensile tests were carried out using a computer-controlled servohydraulic testing machine (810MTS). Tests are performed at room temperature under displacement control. The cross-head displacement rate of the testing machine was 1 mm per minute. A 30 mm gauge length extensometer is used to measure the sample strain. Specimens are loaded up to 50 MPa during the first cycle. Then, for each cycle, a stress increase of 25 MPa is applied, until coupons fail. Stress-strain data were recorded. Aluminium tabs are bonded on specimens. Testing conditions were inspired by the C1275-10 ASTM standard [7].

The microstructure was studied through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a FEI Nova SEM microscope. Before SEM observations, open porosity of samples processed by RTM were filled under vacuum by a low viscosity epoxy resin.

3 Tensile behaviour

This section is divided into two parts. First, composites made using an undiluted resin and, secondly, composites made with a diluted one. Typical stress-strain curves are reported for each material in figures 1, 2 and 3. Figures 4-7 present bar charts of the strength, the yield stress, the modulus of elasticity and the tensile rupture strain for the six considered materials. Moduli of elasticity were determined from the slope of the tangent to the curve at the origin.

3.1 Composites processed with an undiluted resin

Both materials, manufactured with a 2D reinforcement by prepreg and RTM processes, show an elastic and quite brittle behaviour. Indeed, a very limited non linear domain is observed. However, mechanical properties drastically fall when RTM process is used. Strength decreases of about 50% and thus yield stress gets lower too. Rupture strain decreases from 0.37% to 0.26%. Only the modulus of elasticity remains quite unchanged. Strength and modulus of elasticity values of the Prepreg_2D composite are close to results obtained in previous works for ceramic matrix composites [8]: tensile

strengths range from 220 MPa to 420 MPa and moduli of elasticity from 64 GPa to 230 GPa. In this review, only carbon/carbon composites show an elastic and brittle behaviour [9, 10].

The RTM_3D composite is essentially non-linear, from 69 MPa. Its modulus of elasticity is 50 GPa. But, strength and rupture strain are rather high. Indeed, strength is 250 MPa and rupture strain is 0.67%. The unloading-reloading hysteresis loops are narrow. Permanent deformations are observed after unloading. This behaviour was observed by Siron and Lamon on a three-dimensional carbon/carbon composite but with lower mechanical properties [11]. This non linear behaviour is probably partially due to the presence of crimped tows in the 3D preform.

3.2 Composites processed with a diluted resin

All the composites manufactured with a diluted resin exhibit a damage tolerant behaviour. This is a new behaviour characteristic for both 2D reinforced materials which indicates an enhanced damage resistance. This behaviour is especially interesting for structural applications.

When water is added in the matrix precursor:

- Moduli of elasticity are slightly decreased.
- Yield stress levels decrease too. Prepreg_2D material is the more affected with a diminution of about 35%. A 20% decrease is observed for the yield stress of RTM_2D and RTM_3D materials. The Prepreg_2D material behaviour moves from a brittle one to a damage tolerant one. It explains the yield stress drop. However, the decrease is less important for RTM_2D composites. This is explained by the low initial mechanical properties. The yield stress decrease is less important for RTM_3D composite made from a diluted resin too. This is probably due to the unchanged tensile behaviour.
- The rupture strain is increased when water is added in the matrix precursor for all materials. This is a noticeable advantage for structural applications.
- Strength is decreased for the RTM_3D and for Prepreg_2D composites processed with a diluted resin. However, it is improved to 207 MPa instead of 135 MPa for the RTM_2D material.

So, water addition changes the mechanical behaviour of Prepreg_2D composites: the specimen made using a diluted resin shows an highly non linear behaviour. A higher load carrying capability with strain, and residual strain during unloading are observed. However, strengths and moduli of elasticity are slightly decreased. The fiber volume fractions and thicknesses are close for both materials. So, the observed differences will be probably explained by the higher porosity of the Prepreg_2D composite processed with a diluted resin.

The mechanical behaviour of RTM_2D composites is also impacted by a water addition in the resin. They exhibit an enhanced damage resistance and the strain capacity is improved by 40%. Strength is improved by 35%. Modulus of elasticity and yield stress are slightly impacted. The fiber volume fraction is 36% for the material processed with an undiluted resin and 39% for the material manufactured with a diluted one. These variations are due to the thickness variations. Open porosities values are close.

Both 2D reinforced composites made with a diluted resin show a really interesting behaviour for structural applications.

RTM_3D composites do not have a different mechanical behaviour with the dilution of the matrix precursor. All the properties are decreased except the rupture strain. The fiber volume fractions are 38% and 33% for the materials processed respectively with an undiluted and a diluted matrix precursor. These variations are due to the thickness variations.

4 Discussion

This section deals with the interpretation of the effect of the process on the mechanical behaviour by considering microstructural characterization. Figure 8 shows the SEM micrographs of fracture surface and polished cross-section of the fiber/matrix interfaces in the Prepreg_2D composite with undiluted matrix. Figure 9 presents the fracture surface of the Prepreg_2D composite processed with a diluted resin at low magnification. Figures 10-15 are cross section SEM micrographs of longitudinal tows, submitted to tension during tensile tests. For all composites, spaces between yarns are well filled

with matrix as presented in figure 16. Microporosities are randomly dispersed in the matrix. Differences between materials are located inside the tows.

4.1 Composites processed with an undiluted resin

In the Prepreg_2D composite microstructure, tows, represented in figure 10, are well filled. SEM observations reveal the presence of two porosity classes. Nanoporosities are noticeable in the matrix, and microporosities are present at fiber/matrix interfaces. Figure 8 focuses on the fiber/matrix interface. A microporosity is located at the interface. Besides, when the contact between matrix and fiber exists, initial debonding is observed. The figure 9 represents the fracture surface of the Prepreg_2D composite made from a diluted resin at a smaller magnification. The fibers have no matrix left on their surface. So, the grade 1 fiber/matrix bonding seems to be weak.

The glass-ceramic matrices are brittle. During the elastic behaviour, load is shared between the fibers and matrix. When the latter breaks, fibers support instantaneously all the load and this leads to the composite failure. The brittle behaviour of the Prepreg_2D material is close to a monolithic material one.

Figure 11 shows that the filling of the 2D fabric tows is different between prepreg and RTM processes. Only a small quantity of resin is present in the tows for RTM_2D composites. Thus, the total area of the fiber/matrix interfaces in this composite is extremely reduced in comparison with the undiluted prepreg material one. The load transfer between the fibers and the matrix is almost not assumed. The mechanical properties are thus drastically decreased.

The nanoporosity network, which appears in Prepreg_2D composite, is not developed in RTM_2D composite. This is probably because of the too small quantity of resin.

SEM observations in figure 12 show that there is more resin in the tows with a 3D preform. But the filling remains still not complete. The fiber/matrix interface surface is rather high and the load transfer between matrix and fibers is increased. Initial grade2 fiber/matrix debonding was observed in the RTM_3D composite. The good mechanical

properties are certainly due to the combined effects of larger filling of the tows and of the mechanical properties of the 3D reinforcement.

4.2 Composites processed with a diluted resin

For Prepreg_2D composites, results show that a water addition changes the mechanical behaviour: composites exhibit an enhanced strain capability. SEM observations in figure 13 of the material still reveals the presence of two porosity classes: nanoporosities, which are in the matrix, and microporosities, located at fiber/matrix interfaces. However, in this composite made from a diluted resin, microporosities also appear in the matrix, and are present in a larger quantity at the fiber/matrix interfaces and become connected. This could explain the different behaviours observed during tensile tests. Microstructural changes, due to water addition, influence the microcrack and crack propagation. Due to the different porosity classes, microcracks initiation and propagation modes are modified. Microcracks' deviation and branching may occur in the presence of porosity, enhancing the composite strain capability in tension. These observations are in agreement with the open porosity values of 18.4% for the composite manufactured from an undiluted resin and of 20.3% for the material made from a diluted one. Figure 9 shows the damage resistance capability of the composite made from a diluted resin. Multiple matrix microcracks are observed.

For RTM_2D composites, water addition drastically changes the mechanical behaviour too: mechanical properties are enhanced. Figure 14 shows that tows are more filled in the composite made from a diluted resin than in the composite made from an undiluted one. Indeed, the dilution decreases the viscosity of the resin and thus, enhances the flow. Thus, fiber/matrix interface surface is higher and the load transfer between the matrix and fibers is permitted. Chermant [12] and then Lamon [13, 14] describe the damage mechanisms in 2D reinforced CMCs processed by chemical vapor infiltration. First, multiple microcracks are formed in the matrix, perpendicular to the loading direction and are stopped by the fibers and deflected at the fiber/matrix interfaces. These cracks initiate at pores of the matrix between the tows. The cracks are then initiated in the matrix in the transverse and longitudinal tows. At this stage, matrix damage and

fiber/matrix debonding are complete. The load transfer between matrix and fibers is not assumed anymore. Only the fibers are loaded. It is observed through the non-linearities of the unloading-reloading curves. The higher quantity of matrix in the tows makes the composite damage tolerant. Besides, it can be observed that the resin structure (Fig. 14) is closer to the prepreg material (Fig. 10) than to the undiluted RTM one (Fig. 11). Indeed, nanoporosities can be observed.

The high water content increases the resulting microporosities volume in the matrix but the tows are more filled and porosity in the yarns is decreased. This is in agreement with the close values of open porosity for both materials.

For RTM_3D composites, water addition does not change the mechanical behaviour which is still damage tolerant. Mechanical properties are decreased but rupture strain. SEM observations does not show any noticeable change. The damage mechanisms are probably close. Open porosity value is higher for the material processed with a diluted resin. The material processed with a diluted resin is thicker than the material processed with an undiluted one. These characteristics could be one of the origins of the different properties. So, the dilution of the resin seems to have a less promising influence in the composites reinforced with a 3D preform.

5 Conclusions

The results presented in this paper shows:

- the processing route effect on the materials,
- the effect of varying the resin water content on the tensile properties of the composites,
- the influence of the reinforcement type on the materials.

Almost all the composites are interesting depending on the application they are used for. The prepreg process of a 2D reinforcement permits to obtain a brittle composite with quite high mechanical properties: a modulus of elasticity of 70 GPa and a strength close to 266 MPa. The RTM process of a 2D reinforcement does not give an interesting material. However, the RTM process of a 3D reinforcement offers a damage tolerant composite with a modulus of 50 GPa and a strength of 250 MPa.

The dilution of the matrix precursor seems to be an interesting way to obtain new properties. The 2D reinforced composite processed with prepreg process is damage tolerant and offers a strain capability. The composite processed by RTM with a 2D reinforcement is now reliable for structural application and offers a damage resistant behaviour with a strength close to 200 MPa and an interesting strain capability. Dilution of the resin used to manufacture the composite processed with a RTM process and a 3D reinforcement does not bring new properties but may offer a higher damage tolerance.

This research is a first step to modify the processing route of competitive structural composites able to withstand continuous thermal exposure such as in aircraft parts located close to engines. These different considered manufacturing techniques lead to different materials with different properties. Some modifications of the mechanical behaviour, induced by the process, are interesting for structural applications, since they improve the damage tolerance. Building a competitive and structural composite material for aircraft applications, exhibiting all the required properties, such as good modulus, high strength and strain capability, and able to withstand continuous thermal exposure, seems now possible.

Figures

Composite	Process	Reinforcement	Resin
Prepreg_2D	Prepreg	2D fabric (6 layers)	undiluted
			diluted
RTM_2D	RTM	2D fabric (7 layers)	undiluted
			diluted
RTM_3D	RTM	3D preform	undiluted
			diluted

Tab. 1. Considered composite materials.

Composite	Resin	Thickness	V _f	OP
Prepreg_2D	undiluted	1.78 mm	38%	18.4%
	diluted	1.75 mm	39%	20.3%
RTM_2D	undiluted	2.30 mm	36%	25.1%
	diluted	2.10 mm	39%	25.2%
RTM_3D	undiluted	2.36 mm	38%	27.1%
	diluted	2.74 mm	33%	28.1%

Tab. 2. Thickness, fiber volume fraction and open porosity of the composite samples.

Fig. 1. Tensile test curves of glass-ceramic matrix composite materials made by prepreg process with 2D reinforcement.

Fig. 2. Tensile test curves of glass-ceramic matrix composite materials made by RTM with 2D reinforcement.

Fig. 3. Tensile test curves of glass-ceramic matrix composite materials made by RTM with 3D preform.

Fig. 4. Modulus of elasticity of the 6 considered glass-ceramic matrix composite materials.

Fig. 5. Strength of the 6 considered glass-ceramic matrix composite materials.

Fig. 6. Yield stress of the 6 considered glass-ceramic matrix composite materials.

Fig. 7. Rupture strain of the 6 considered glass-ceramic matrix composite materials.

Fig. 9. SEM micrograph of a fracture surface of the Prepreg_2D composite processed with a diluted resin.

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of fiber/matrix interfaces in the Prepreg_2D composite processed with an undiluted resin.

Fig. 10. SEM micrograph of a Prepreg_2D sample processed with an undiluted resin (longitudinal tow).

Fig. 11. SEM micrograph of a RTM_2D sample processed with an undiluted resin (longitudinal tow).

Fig. 12. SEM micrograph of a RTM_3D sample processed with an undiluted resin (longitudinal tow).

Fig. 15. SEM micrograph of a RTM_3D sample processed with a diluted resin (longitudinal tow).

Fig. 13. SEM micrograph of a Prepreg_2D sample processed with a diluted resin (longitudinal tow).

Fig. 16. SEM micrograph of a RTM_2D sample processed with an undiluted resin (cross-section between tows).

Fig. 14. SEM micrograph of a RTM_2D sample processed with a diluted resin (longitudinal tow).

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